

MODERN STELLAR ASTRONOMY

Binary stars and planetary systems in the Orion Nebula Cluster

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Gaia DR3 photometry data have revealed new resolved binary systems in the Orion Nebula Cluster (ONC). The previously compiled list of ONC stars [1] in the region of the sky where free-floating planet and stars with planetary systems were discovered using the James Webb Telescope (JWST) was used. The technique of searching for binary stars in the Gaia DR3 catalog [5] was applied. The results allowed us to refine the number of binary stars in the central part of the ONC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Previously, [1] conducted a study of the central part of the Orion Nebula Cluster (ONC) using Gaia DR3 data. Candidate stars for ONC were selected. The probabilities of membership of stars in ONC were estimated. The study was conducted for the selected region of the sky of JWST observations, where free-floating planets and stars with planetary systems were detected, which overlaps in space with the Orion Nebula (M 42). The region is characterized by a patchy structure of the distribution of stars, the presence of cold (10K) and hot (10000K) dust and gas, as well as X-ray radiation.

2. DATA

The previously compiled list of ONC stars [1] was used in the region of the sky where free-floating planets and stars with planetary systems were discovered using the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). Stars by their position in the sky (equatorial coordinates $RA_{ICRS} : 83.7^\circ - 83.9^\circ$; $DE_{ICRS} : -5.5^\circ \div -5.3^\circ$ and $Plx > 1$ mas) were selected from [2] using VizieR. The size of the region is 0.2° by 0.2° ($\sim 1.4 \times 1.4$ pc at a distance of ONC from the Sun $d = 398.3 \pm 15.5$ pc – based on the parallaxes of Gaia DR3 stars [2]).

3. SEARCH FOR STAR-PLANET PAIRS

A near-infrared survey by the James Webb Space Telescope has found 540 free Jupiter Mass Objects (JuMOs) ranging from 0.6 to $14 M_{Jup}$ and 42 free Jupiter Mass Binary Objects (JuMBOs) [3]. They are located in the region of the sky where the Trapezium of Orion is located. The predicted separation of the

components is between 25 AU and 380 AU. Two of these objects have a nearby third companion with a mass similar to that of Jupiter.

We analyzed the proximity of stars and free-floating binary planets (JuMBO) in the sky, Fig. 1. For this purpose, pairs of "star - binary planet" were selected. With an angular distance of $r = 0.002865^\circ$ (linear ~ 0.01 pc at $d = 400$ pc), the number of pairs was $n = 19$, a list of which is given [1].

4. DATA FROM SIMBAD

The region under consideration contains isolated binary systems [4]. This was confirmed by our search in

Figure 1. Position of stars in the sky taken from Gaia DR3 and JuMBO. The color scale on the right shows the probability of a star belonging to a cluster. Blue dots ($n = 748$), and JuMBO ($n = 42$ [3]) are green dots. The JuMBO observation area is $0.15^\circ \times 0.2^\circ$. The distribution of stars in our list by probability is as follows: stars with $P \geq 50\%$ - (26 stars); $30 \leq P \leq 50\%$ - (12); $10 \leq P < 30\%$ - (32).

SIMBAD, which yielded 3 stars from the WDS-Washington Visual Double Star Catalog and one possible binary (Children-2), Table 1. Note that most of the stars are YSOs. A young stellar object (YSO) denotes a star in the early stage of its evolution. This class consists of two groups of objects: protostars and pre-main sequence stars.

5. METOD OF SEARCHING FOR BINARY STARS IN THE GAIA DR3 CATALOGUE

The technique proposed by [5] was used. For a resolved binary with an angular separation within a few arcseconds, the BP and RP quantities represent the combined flux from the system, while the angular resolution in the G band allows one to obtain the individual brightness of the star. The BP and RP fluxes are efficiently measured using aperture photometry in a fairly large window of $3.5 \times 2.1''$ [6], while the G quantities are obtained by fitting a line spread function optimized for point sources [7]. As a result, for a resolved binary with an angular separation within a few arcseconds, the BP and RP quantities represent the combined flux from the system, while the angular resolution in the G band allows one to obtain the individual brightness of the star. Gaia DR3 photometry data have revealed new resolved binary systems in the Orion Nebula Cluster (ONC), Table 2.

6. PARAMETERS OF BINARY SYSTEMS

The distance between the stars in a binary system a can range from less than one astronomical unit to several hundred AU. In our case, if the gravitational connection between stars is proven, the distance of the binary star from the Sun is $dist \approx 400$ pc. For a resolved binary with an angular separation $\alpha = 0.00056^\circ$, $a = dist \times \sin\alpha$. That means $a \approx 0.004pc$, or $a = 0.004 \times 206265 \approx 800$ AU.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A search for possible binaries in our region was performed for all stars. 14 pairs were found. The final data are contained in Table 3.

Evolution of binary systems. The low fraction of binary systems found in ONC is indicative of young cluster dynamics. In dense environments, loosely bound wide pairs can quickly disintegrate. Therefore, binary systems in ONC are either initially very close (and therefore unresolved by Gaia), or have a moderate separation of \approx hundreds of AU and are "stable" systems.

Origin of planet-like objects. For free-floating planet-like objects observed with JWST, two scenarios are considered: (1) single formation directly from the cloud core (i.e. as a low-mass star) (2) formation in a stellar system with subsequent ejection. ONC data show that many of these objects are very young (bright

IR sources), which partially supports the first scenario. However, the presence of close stellar companions also points to a role for the second scenario. Probably, both mechanisms contribute.

Triple multiple systems. Future releases of Gaia (DR4/DR5) will allow better resolution of these structures. Cluster dynamics. ONC is expected to disintegrate in a few tens of millions of years, with free-floating planets and stars scattered throughout the Galaxy. In this process, wide binary systems are expected to further disintegrate. Thus, ONC observations provide an important snapshot of multiple systems on the early evolution of a star cluster.

Future research (proposals). Deep Gaia analysis. Future versions of the Gaia data (DR4 and beyond) will provide solutions for binary systems in the ONC. In particular, astrometric solutions and variable light curves will allow us to identify systems with separations <100 AU. This will help to quantify how incomplete the detected fraction of binary systems is ($\sim 4\%$). JWST spectroscopy will allow us to determine the age and mass of JuMBOs. Unexpected molecular signals (e.g., PAHs (Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons)) require theoretical explanation. N-body modeling. For the ONC (~ 2000 stars [9]), we need to model the conditions under which 42 JuMBOs and ~ 500 JuMOs arise (extending the work [8]). Comparison with other clusters. Analysis of IC 348, NGC 1333 will show whether ONC is unique in its number of free-floating planets.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this work declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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¹ <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/gaia>

² <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dpac/consortium>

³ <http://cds.u-strasbg.fr>

Table 1. SIMBAD data for stars (including WDS) of our sample with membership probability $P \geq 0.5$

ID Gaia	P	RUWE	dist, pc	WDS	Type
017364132050194688	0.98	1.485	378.4	WDS J05353-523Aa,Ab	Herbig Ae/Be Star
3017360146320757888	0.97	1.001	410.39		Young Stellar Object
3017266206784582144	0.97	1.107	394.52		Orion Variable
3017360249399928832	0.97	0.867	389.77		T Tauri Star
3017366743390006144	0.96	0.768	401.46		Young Stellar Object
3017366709030057600	0.94	1.008	412.81		Orion Variable
3017364613086735360	0.94	1.167	397.44		Orion Variable
3017364132041596288	0.93	0.607	396.51		
3017364059023825280	0.92	1.434	406.55		Orion Variable
3017364368261463936	0.89	1.321	380.65	Children=2	Orion Variable
3017362551501920640	0.87	0.834	414.92		Orion Variable
3017359149888300928	0.85	0.893	415.47		Orion Variable
3017360180680489600	0.83	0.823	407.68		Young Stellar Object
3017363410495899136	0.82	1.187	390.53		Orion Variable
3017363376136167936	0.75	2.229	493.51		BY Dra Variable
3017364441289875712	0.75	0.955	387.01		Orion Variable
3017366743389340416	0.74	0.834	378.36		Young Stellar Object
3017266309864085632	0.70	0.890	384.78		Young Stellar Object
3017361074033180928	0.69	1.034	398.74		Orion Variable
3017361142752677376	0.65	0.634	367.48		Young Stellar Object
3017364132041551744	0.63	0.882	437.33		Dense Core
3017360833515044480	0.60	1.012	418.94	WDS J05354-0525B	Young Stellar Object
3017359390406490496	0.56	0.874	413.58		Young Stellar Object
3017364303848916992	0.54	0.644	386.73	WDS J05351-0522B	YSO Candidate
3017364235132349952	0.53	0.827	391.04		YSO Candidate
3209518975997993216	0.53	1.007	396.13		Young Stellar Object

 Table 2. SIMBAD data for sample stars with membership probability $P \geq 0.0$

N ^o	RA_ICRS (deg)	DE_ICRS (deg)	Plx (mas)	RUWE	Gmag	BPmag	RPmag
1	83.7861640	-5.4837734	2.3057	0.896	16.9336	18.5894	15.4281
	83.7866347	-5.4838281	2.3767	1.064	18.2396		
2	83.7593042	-5.4860799	2.5285	0.979	16.8973		
	83.7590036	-5.4860852	2.8747	1.690	15.8238	16.5934	14.3053
3	83.8052059	-5.4650857	2.3818	0.706	16.1199	16.6367	14.4672
	83.8049813	-5.4646875	2.5176	0.929	18.5822		
4	83.8430297	-5.4039634	2.4925	1.002	14.8594	12.7220	11.9682
	83.8434832	-5.4037424	3.0056	0.452	17.8306		
5	83.8623466	-5.4001057	2.5246	1.991	17.2995	14.1515	13.4110
	83.8624459	-5.4002403	2.1098	1.076	17.1802	14.1724	13.4100
6	83.8492025	-5.3928602	2.4712	0.920	15.4426	13.9504	12.9648
	83.8495252	-5.3925607	2.4156	1.117	17.6660		
7	83.7406007	-5.3976507	2.7586	1.065	13.9963		
	83.7407469	-5.3979565	2.5506	1.266	13.3928	13.9733	11.9973
8	83.7680873	-5.3870276	1.9070	0.832	16.4060		
	83.7682491	-5.3872169	1.3886	2.691	14.5712	14.9405	13.1721
9	83.8121858	-5.4035765	1.5794	1.619	16.0854	13.2201	12.3633
	83.8120582	-5.4032684	2.5239	0.441	16.1485	13.3643	12.3982
10	83.8160072	-5.3895762	1.9486	1.629	13.4661	12.1951	11.2101
	83.8155555	-5.3895814	2.4449	0.799	13.8721	12.3131	11.4142
11	83.8205869	-5.3723884	4.3990	0.331	18.2454		
	83.8203865	-5.3729029	2.4312	0.914	13.8430	13.0676	11.8678
12	83.7937263	-5.3793667	2.2938	1.858	13.7023	13.1504	11.9706
	83.7941102	-5.3790982	2.6207	1.106	15.7789		
13	83.8562015	-5.3598766	2.3980	0.862	15.9331	14.8791	13.6087
	83.8561330	-5.3595574	2.4216	0.795	16.7340	16.3733	14.3312
14	83.8246829	-5.3487259	2.5658	1.460	17.0314		
	83.8243671	-5.3483408	2.5650	0.964	14.2729	14.2605	12.7259

Table 3. Numbers of different objects in the central part of ONC.

the number, n	source
single stars	454, GDR3 [2]
binary stars	4 (WDS)+14 (method [5])
stars with one planet	~ 150 [8]
single isolated planets	500, JWST [3]
free-floating binary planets	42, JWST [3]

VizieR catalog access tool, CDS, Strasbourg, France (DOI: 10.26093/cds/vizier). The original description of the VizieR service was published in 2000, A&AS **143**, 23. Authors are grateful reviewer for useful remarks that allowed to improve our work.

- [1] Vereshchagin S.V., Tagaev D. I., Bugra Keskin T., et al., *Astron. Rep.* **69**, 3, 157–168 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1134/S106377292570163X>
- [2] Gaia Collaboration, 2023 <https://doi.org/10.5270/esa-qa4lep3>
- [3] Pearson S. G. and McCaughrean M. J., arXiv:2310.01231 (2023). <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2023arXiv231001231P>
- [4] Jerabkova T., Beccari G., Boffin H. M. J., et al., *A&A* **627**, A57 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935016>
- [5] Chulkov, D., *AJ* **168**, 4, id.156, 13 pp. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ad7025>
- [6] Riello, M., De Angeli, F., Evans, D. W., et al., *A&A* **649**, A3 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039587>
- [7] Rowell, N., Davidson, M., Lindegren, L., et al., *A&A* **649**, A11 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039448>
- [8] Limbach M. A., Soares-Furtado M., Vanderburg A., et al., *PASP*, **135**, 014401 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/acafa4>
- [9] Morales-Calderón M., Stauffer J. R., Hillenbrand L. A., et al., *ApJ* **733**, 50 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/733/1/50>